

Research Article

Mathematical Innovations based on Rotation, Finite Elements and Geometric Modelling of the Tangram Puzzle

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Abstract: *This paper presents the development of mathematical applications grounded in rotation, finite element analysis, and geometric modelling, specifically centred on the Tangram puzzle. We investigate the role of rotational symmetries in enhancing puzzle-solving strategies, demonstrating how these principles can optimize the arrangement and configuration of Tangram pieces. By employing mathematical principles of rotation, efficient methods for piece manipulation and arrangement that can simplify complex puzzle solutions are revealed. Utilizing finite element methods, we analyze the geometric properties and structural integrity of Tangram pieces. This analysis provides valuable insights into the relationships among the shapes, revealing how they interact within various configurations. These insights have potential applications in design and engineering, where understanding structural relationships is crucial. Furthermore, we employ geometric modelling techniques to create interactive visualizations that illustrate the transformations and manipulations of Tangram pieces. These visualizations not only enhance understanding but also engage users in exploring geometric concepts dynamically. For each of the three mathematical concepts discussed, we provide several applications in the form of MATLAB GUI tools, illustrating their real-world potential. The results emphasize the Tangram puzzle as a dynamic educational tool that fosters creativity and encourages critical thinking. This work contributes to integrating traditional puzzles into modern mathematical applications, promoting innovative approaches in both education and research.*

Keywords: matrices; mesh object; paraboloid.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tangrams are a traditional Chinese dissection puzzle consisting of seven flat pieces known as tans, which can be arranged to form a square as well as various shapes, such as animals, people, and objects. The puzzle originated in China in the early 19th century and gained popularity in the West

during the 19th and 20th centuries. Each of the seven tans includes two large triangles, one medium triangle, two small triangles, one square, and one parallelogram.

When playing the puzzle, the challenge lies not only in constructing the square from the tans but also in rearranging them to create specific figures without overlapping any pieces. In addition to being a delightful pastime, tangrams serve educational purposes by helping students develop skills in geometry, spatial reasoning and problem-solving. Engaging with tangrams allows learners to explore mathematical concepts such as congruence, symmetry, and area in a hands-on manner. As an interactive tool, tangrams encourage creativity and critical thinking, making them a popular choice for classroom activities and STEM learning. With their rich cultural heritage and versatility, tangrams remain a valuable resource for both fun and education in mathematics.

This paper presents and discusses several mathematical concepts related to the tangram puzzle, including rotational symmetry, finite element analysis and also geometric modelling. Several mathematical applications in Matlab GUI that are related to the concepts are presented to highlight their potential real-world applications. By demonstrating the practical applications of these mathematical principles, this paper showcases how the traditional Tangram puzzle can serve as an effective educational tool for teaching complex mathematical concepts, thereby fostering education and research in mathematics.

2. A FEW MATHEMATICAL CONCEPTS IN TANGRAM PUZZLE

Consider the challenge of constructing a square from the 7 pieces of tans given in Figure 1. In order to create the square, as shown in Figure 2, several tans will need to undergo linear transformations. For example, one of the large triangles must be rotated clockwise by 90° to become the piece number 4 of the square in Figure 2. However, the shape and the size of the triangle will not change after the rotation, as expected. This suggests that tangram teaches rotation and its properties.

Figure 1. The seven pieces of tan in the Tangram puzzle.

Figure 2. A square that can be created by all tans.

Moreover, as can be seen in Figure 2, all tans are used to create the square. If the tans are called as the elements needed to create the square, then the square are created by the finite number of elements. In the field of computational mathematics, the finite element method (FEM) is one of the most important techniques for solving complex mathematical problems. Typically, the domain of interest is divided into a finite number of shapes, such as triangles or squares, before any computations are conducted. Each shape (or element) plays a crucial role, as it represents a part of the original domain and can be analyzed to gain insights into the overall characteristics of that domain. Now, suppose the domain under consideration is the square shown in Figure 2, which consists of seven elements (tans). The area of the square can be calculated as the sum of the areas of all the tans. This value of the area might be important for evaluating the accuracy of the numerical results or any simulations related to the problems.

Another mathematical concept in Tangram examined in this study is a mathematical model, specifically, the geometric model. Suppose that all tans are rearranged to create the model of a house in Figure 3. The manipulation of tangram pieces encourages the development of spatial reasoning, allowing learners to experiment with different configurations to form new shapes while maintaining the same total area. This not only enhances an understanding of how geometric concepts apply to real-world objects but also underscores the importance of reconstruction, where individual elements are pieced together to create a cohesive whole. Besides, rearranging tangram pieces promotes critical problem-solving skills and provides valuable insights into how objects are modelled and transformed in both theoretical and practical contexts. For example, if all the tans are used to model a fish, as shown in Figure 4, the modeler might want to explain the difference between the model and a real fish, noting that the geometry of a real fish should include curves. In this way, tangrams function as a bridge between fundamental geometric principles and the broader realm of modelling, offering a dynamic and engaging means of exploring how simple shapes can be combined to represent complex systems or structures across various fields.

Figure 3. A model of a house, created by all tans.

Figure 4. A model of a fish, created by all tans.

3. MATHEMATICAL INNOVATIONS

For each mathematical concept described in the previous section, this section presents previously developed mathematical innovations that can be related to each concept.

3.1 Rotation

Consider a spheroid in the Cartesian coordinate system given $x^2 + \left(\frac{y+z}{2}\right)^2 = 1$. In the applications of metal detection, the spheroid can be represented by the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 32 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 68 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 68 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where, if the spheroid is rotated counterclockwise around the z -axis by 90° , such that the Cartesian equation of the rotated spheroid becomes $\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)^2 + y^2 + \left(\frac{z}{2}\right)^2 = 1$, the rotated spheroid can then be represented by another matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 68 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 32 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 68 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The relationship between (1) and (2) is actually given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} 68 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 32 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 68 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos 90^\circ & \sin 90^\circ & 0 \\ -\sin 90^\circ & \cos 90^\circ & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 32 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 68 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 68 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos 90^\circ & -\sin 90^\circ & 0 \\ \sin 90^\circ & \cos 90^\circ & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

This means, if the original spheroid rotates then the matrix representation also rotates. Figure 5 shows a MATLAB Graphical User Interface (GUI) that is developed to compute the matrix, called as the first order polarization tensor, for any spheroid $\left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y+z}{b}\right)^2 = 1$ (where a and b are the semi axes) with conductivity k (representing the material of the spheroid), before and after the spheroid is rotated one time around any of the coordinate axis.

Figure 5. The overall layout of the application Spheroidal First Order Polarization Tensor Calculator with One Time Rotation as the Matlab GUI.

The application in Figure 5 has been developed by Abdul Latiff et al. (2024) and since it computes the first order polarization tensor for rotated spheroids, it is called as Spheroidal First Order Polarization Tensor Calculator with One Time Rotation (simplified as RSFOPT1). The invention is an extension of our application presented in Mohamad Yunos et al. (2024) that has been copyrighted under MyIPO with reference number LY2024J02487. The previous invention can only calculate the first order polarization tensor for the spheroid based on the Cartesian equation of the spheroid whereas the in the current invention, a new feature is included to allow the calculation of the first order PT for a spheroid, after the spheroid is rotated one time around any of the coordinate axis. Both Matlab GUIs could be useful in describing those spheroids in the applications of metal detection such as in security screening, medical imaging or landmine clearance. For convenience, Figure 6 is provided to illustrate another example of using the latest application.

Figure 6. The interface when using the GUI with inputs conductivity, $k=100000000$, semi axes, $a=0.014$, and $b=0.0128$ with $\theta=120^\circ$.

3.2 Finite Elements

Our next invention is related to the finite elements of tan in tangram. The invention called as the Mesh Objects Info is also a Matlab GUI, and has been presented in Ahmad Khairuddin et al. (2024-1). Figure 7 shows the layout of the application. Basically, the application can display a 3D object that has been partitioned into a finite number of triangles (for its surface) and tetrahedra (for its volume) after the object is uploaded. Since the 3D object consists of finite elements (triangles and tetrahedra), the object is often called as the mesh object.

Besides displaying the mesh object, the volume and the surface area of the mesh object are also calculated by the application. Like the surface area of the tangram in Figure 2, the surface area of the mesh object is calculated by adding up the areas of all triangles on the surface. Meanwhile, the volume is calculated by finding the total volume of all tetrahedra. The application has been copyrighted under MyIPO with reference number LY2022J01470. This application could be very useful in many applications of science and engineering especially when the FEM is applied.

Figure 7. The overall layout of the application Mesh Objects Info.

Figure 8 and Figure 9 show two examples in using the application. Since the cube in Figure 8 is a polyhedron built up from a combination of polygons, namely the triangles (on the surface), and another polyhedron, namely the tetrahedra (for the volume), the values calculated for the surface area and volume are indeed accurate for a cube with dimensions $1 \times 1 \times 1$. Meanwhile, the surface area and the volume for the sphere given in Figure 9 are close to $4\pi \approx 12.57$ and $4\pi/3 \approx 4.19$, respectively, which are the volume and the surface area of the sphere with radius 1. Since sphere is a curved geometry, some errors may arise when polygons and polyhedra are used to build it. The accuracies of the surface area and the volume of the mesh object representing the sphere can be increased by using a larger number of the elements when constructing the mesh. Determining the values of the surface area or the volume of the mesh object of a particular problem could be crucial in getting the correct results about the problem. In this case, one might want to ensure that the volume or the surface area of the mesh object is closer to the exact value before performing any computation involving the mesh object.

Figure 8. The outputs when using Mesh Objects Info with the mesh object represents a cube.

Figure 9. The outputs when using Mesh Objects Info with the mesh object represents a sphere.

3.3 Geometric Model

In this section, we first consider the solid geometry in the 3D Cartesian coordinate system where, the solid is above the xy -plane and bounded by the circular parabola given by

$$z = -\frac{h}{r^2}(x^2 + y^2) + h, \tag{4}$$

where, r is the radius of the circular base of the parabola and h is the height of the parabola (see Figure 10). The volume, V of the solid can be obtained by using the formula

$$V = \frac{\pi r^2 h}{2} \tag{5}$$

while the surface area, S of the solid (not include the circular base) is given by

$$S = \frac{\pi r [(4h^2 + r^2)^{3/2} - r^3]}{6h^2} + \pi r^2. \tag{6}$$

Figure 11 shows the layout of a Matlab GUI that has been developed by Kamarudin et al. (2024) that can display the paraboloid solid together with its volume and surface area. The application is called as Visualization and Some Properties of a Paraboloid Shaped Object and has been copyrighted under MyIPO with reference number LY2024J05921. In order to use the application, user only need to specify the values of r and h before clicking the button RUN to get the outputs.

Figure 10. A schematic diagram of a circular parabola with height, h and radius, r .

Figure 11. The overall layout of the Matlab GUI, Visualization and Some Properties of a Paraboloid Shaped Object

As an example, Figure 12 is given to show all outputs of the application with the values $r = 1$ and $h = 2$. In Kamarudin et al. (2024), it is shown that the application has been used to model a dome, a satellite and also a charcoal kiln. Using a paraboloid to model real-world objects is similar to using tangram pieces to model the house and the fish shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively. Although further investigations are needed to verify the models, the application seems able to provide initial insights about the modelled object. In Ahmad Khairuddin et al. (2024-2), the application is discussed in more details when it is used to model a charcoal kiln using the data provided from surveying technology terrestrial laser scanning.

Figure 11. The overall layout of the Matlab GUI, Visualization and Some Properties of a Paraboloid Shaped Object

4. POTENTIAL COMMERCIALIZATIONS OF THE INNOVATIONS

For each mathematical innovation provided in this paper, its commercialization potentials are already described in the related references. However, this paper recommends including tangram puzzles when commercializing each invention in education. Furthermore, integrating tangram puzzles into educational curricula can spark interest in mathematical research, encouraging students to investigate patterns, develop problem-solving strategies, and engage in collaborative learning experiences that enhance their understanding of both mathematics and the innovations being studied.

5. CONCLUSION

Integrating tangram puzzles into educational and research settings not only enriches the learning experience but also serves as a bridge between mathematical concepts and innovative thinking. These puzzles serve as an effective tool for teaching mathematical concepts such as geometry, spatial reasoning, and symmetry, allowing students to explore and apply these ideas in a tangible way. Ultimately, the combination of tangram puzzles and mathematical innovation can inspire creativity and a deeper understanding of mathematical principles, paving the way for future discoveries and advancements.

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